

**SINGLE DOSE TOXICITY STUDY OF AN AYURVEDIC MEDICINE:
VAIKRANTA BHASMA (BLACK TOURMALINE ASH)**

***Tripathi R.¹, Rathore A.S.¹, Mehra B.L.², Raghubeer R.³**

Deptt. Of Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, R.G.G.P.G. Ayurvedic College and Hospital,
Paprola (H.P.)

Deptt. of Kaya Chikitsa, R.G.G.P.G. Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Paprola (H.P.)

Central Drug Research Institutue, Lucknow

Article Received on
11 March 2013,
Revised on 10 April 2013,
Accepted on 28 April 2013

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17605547>

***Correspondence for
Author:**

Dr. Rituraj Tripathi

10/105, Awas Vikas Yojna -3,
Near Pollution Control Board
Office, Jhunsi, Allahabad
(U.P.) India.

dr.riturajtripathi@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In ayurveda metals and minerals are therapeutically used only in the form of bhasma. Vaikranta (black tourmaline) bhasma is a herbo-mineral preparation used in ayurvedic medicine as rejuvenator and aphrodisiac. In order to assess and evaluate the toxicity profile of vaikranta bhasma and to determine its adverse effects, a Single dose toxicity study in CF rats was performed. The test protocol for this purpose was designed to obtain information on possible health hazards likely to arise in the test species from a single exposure of the test material by oral route. The animals were observed for fourteen days after single exposure to vaikranta bhasma, and various parameters indicative of systemic toxic effects were examined and evaluated. The study was intended to provide an estimate of the dose which was likely to be free of toxic effects on single exposure through oral route.

Key words: Vaikranta, Bhasma, Toxicity, Tourmaline.

INRODUCTION

Toxicology is the study of harmful effects of substances on living organisms, humans, plants and animals. Toxicological testing evaluates the biological response of living organisms to different routes and durations of exposure to a substance. The toxicological study determines what doses of drug are harmful and what doses would not be expected to pose unreasonable risk.

All drugs should be evaluated for acute, sub-chronic and chronic effects. Acute toxicological testing evaluates whether a single high-dose exposure to a substance will produce acute effects or not (An acute effect could be anything from a skin rash to death.). To meet the regulatory requirements, various toxicological studies can be broadly categorized into systemic, special, local and carcinogenic testing.

Bhasma literally means “ash”. But in ayurveda, bhasma is a unique herbo-mineral preparation of metals and minerals associated with organic macromolecules derived from herbal extracts by alchemic process making these biologically assimilable. In ayurveda metals and minerals are therapeutically used only in the form of bhasma. Vaikranta bhasma is a herbo-mineral preparation used in ayurvedic medicine as rejuvenator and aphrodisiac. For therapeutic purpose black tourmaline or iron tourmaline or schorl should be taken as vaikranta.¹ In the present study vaikranta (black tourmaline), gandhaka (sulphur), kulattha (*Dolichos biflorous*), milk, ghrita, and lemon juice were used to prepare vaikranta bhasma. This method is described in ayurveda book “Rasa Ratna Samucchaya”.²

There is an ayurvedic principle stating that the greatest of all remedies, taken improperly, can be a poison; and the worst poison, taken properly, can be the greatest of remedies. In order to assess and evaluate the toxicity profile of vaikranta bhasma and to determine its adverse effects, a Single dose toxicity study in CF rats was performed. The test protocol for this purpose was designed to obtain information on possible health hazards likely to arise in the test species from a single exposure of the test material by oral route. The study intended to provide an estimate of the dose which was likely to be free of toxic effects on single exposure through oral route.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Standardized test material prepared at R.G.G.P.G. Ayu. College, Paprola (H.P.) 176115 was supplied to the Division of Toxicology, CDRI, Lucknow in required amount. It was packed in a polythene bag and kept inside a screw-capped, opaque plastic container.

A total of 20 young, adult albino rats of CF strain were supplied by the Division of Laboratory Animals, C.D.R.I., Lucknow. From this group, 15 animals showing evidence of good health were selected on the basis of findings of their initial health check-up and body weight recordings. They were randomly assigned to two treatment groups each consisting of five rats. An additional group comprising of an equal number of animals receiving vehicle

per se (Gum acacia) in identical manner served as control. Group mean value of body weights of animals ranged between 160.20 gm to 177.30 gm at the time of their recruitment in the study. Animals were acclimatized to the laboratory conditions for 7 days prior to the test.

Five animals of each group were housed together in a Polypropylene, autoclavable cage (Dimensions: 43x27x15 cm³) with steel wire-mesh lid having provisions for attaching water bottle and for keeping food pellets. Bedding husk was changed daily. Temperature and relative humidity in the experimental animal room were maintained at target levels of 24±2°C and between 30-70%, respectively. Throughout the study, a sequence of 12 hourly cycles of light and darkness was maintained in the room with the help of artificial lighting. Water was provided ad libitum by means of water feeding bottles fitted with a nozzle. For feeding, conventional commercially available laboratory pelleted diet (M/S Ashirvad Industries, Chandigarh) was provided ad libitum through the container of appropriate size made in the wire-mesh lid of the cages. Initial identity marking of animals was done by 1% aqueous eosin, and final identity marking (after selection and random grouping) of animals was done by saturated solution of picric acid. Each cage house of the animals was labeled appropriately showing the study number, group number, animal number, date of start of study, date of termination of study

The test material (vaikranta bhasma), in the dose of **10.50 mg/kg and 21.0 mg/kg** body weight, suspended in vehicle (gum acacia) was administered once by oral route to CF rats of treated group. Control group of animals received vehicle in an identical manner. Detail description is given in table no. 1.

Table No. 1: Study design

Dose Group		Animals Number		Daily Oral Treatment
		No.	I.D.	
Gp I	Control	5	1-5	<i>Gum acacia</i> (10ml/kg b.wt)
Gp II	Low Dose	5	6-10	10.5 mg of TM/kg b.wt. (suspended in 1 % Gum Acacia)
Gp III	High Dose	5	11-14	21 mg of TM/kg b.wt. (suspended in 1 % Gum Acacia)

OBSERVATION PARAMETERS

Following this, the animals were observed daily for 14 days to detect any signs of toxicity. Initial and final body weights and food/water consumption of the animals were recorded. Terminal recordings of haematological and blood biochemical parameters of the animals were done. All the animals were sacrificed and necropsied at the end of the study. Necropsy included complete examination of the external surface of the body, all orifices, and the cranial, thoracic and abdominal cavities, and their contents. A thorough naked eye examination of size, shape, surface, contours etc. of all the important tissue and organs was done. Weights of brain, heart, liver, kidneys, adrenals, spleen, lungs and gonads were recorded and their relative organ weights (g/100g b.wt.) were also calculated. All the above organs, and pieces from skin, trachea, thyroid, eyes, different parts of the gastro-intestinal tract and pancreas were processed for paraffin embedding, sectioning and microscopic examination. Observation parameters and methodology is described in table no. 2

Table 2; Observation parameters and methodology at a glance

S.No.	Observation Parameters	Time
1.	Cage-Side Observations: General appearance, Activity, Behaviour, Eyes, Fur-coat, Mucous membranes, Body orifices, Consistency of excreta	Daily
2.	Mortality/Morbidity	Daily
3.	Body Weight	Initial/ Final
4.	24-Hour Food Consumption	Initial/ Final
5.	Haematology¹: (Hb, T-RBC, MCV, MCHC, HCT, TLC, DLC, Platelet Count)	Terminal
6.	Blood Biochemistry² (Glu, Chol, TG, T-Prot, Alb, Glob, T-Bil, ALP, ALT, AST, BUN, Creat, Ca ²⁺ , P)	Terminal
7.	Sacrifice/Necropsy/Histopathology³ : Gross and Microscopic examination of important organs and tissues (viz, adrenal, brain, heart, gonads, kidneys, liver, lungs, spleen, skin, eyes, trachea, thyroid, pancreas, stomach, duodenum, jejunum, colon). Absolute/relative weights and histology of adrenal, brain, heart, gonads, kidneys, liver, lungs and spleen.	Terminal

¹Make/Model of Analyser: MS-9, Melet Schlosing. Standard chemicals and reagents supplied by the same company were used.

²Make/Model of Analyser: Beckman Synchron CX5 Clinical Chemistry analyser. Standard kits supplied by M/S Beckman were used.

³Methods and techniques described in “Theory and Practice of Histological Techniques”, 3rd Ed, JD Bancroft and A Stevens (Eds), 1990. Churchill Livingstone, Longman Group UK Ltd. [Chapters 2 (pp. 21-42), 3 (pp. 43-60), 4 (pp. 61-80) and 7 (pp. 107-118)] were used.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Raw data was processed to get group means and standard deviations. Intergroup comparison of data was done by one way ANOVA.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General Observations and Mortality

Animals of treated and control groups remained generally active and healthy during the period of the study. Fur coat, nasal mucosa, eyes and conjunctivae remained normal. There was no redness or discharge from the mucosal membranes and body orifices. Findings of general observations are being summarized below:

Appearance	:	All Normal
Activity	:	Normal
Fur Coat	:	Clean and healthy in all the animals
Mucous Membranes	:	No abnormality could be detected
Body Orifices	:	Clean and healthy in all the animals
Eyes	:	Normal, No Discharge
Excreta	:	Normal. No diarrhoea.

No mortality was seen in any of the group both treated and control.

Body Weights

There was a uniform and comparable gain in body weight among the animals of drug-treated and control groups.

Food and Water Consumption

Monitoring by measurement of the initial and leftover water and solid diet (pellets) in the containers revealed irregular variations in the average 24-hour water and food intake of animals in the control and treated groups. There was no evidence of any effect of treatment with the test material

Laboratory Investigations

Haematology

The following observations were made while comparing the mean values of the different haematological parameters of treated and control groups of animals:

Haemoglobin, T-RBC Count, Mean Corpuscular Haemoglobin Concentration (MCHC), Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV), Haematocrit (Hct)

There were irregular variations (<10%) in the final levels of RBC parameters of the animals of the treated and control groups. These changes did not show any dose or treatment related changes and were within the normal physiological range.

Total Leucocyte Count (TLC) and Differential Leucocyte Count (DLC)

Irregular patterns of changes were seen in the mean TLC values of treated and control animals of all the groups. Mean values ranged from 14600 to 17500/cu.mm. Mean values of neutrophil and lymphocyte percentage also showed irregular variations in all the animals of treated and control groups. Polymorph percentage ranged between 13.0 to 14.2 %. Lymphocyte percentage ranged between 79.8 to 81.2 %. All these values were well within the range of normalcy in both treated and control animals.

Platelet Count

The variations observed in control and treated rats were well comparable and within the limits of normalcy. Mean values of platelet counts varied between 3.02 to 3.27 lac/cu.mm.

Table no. 3: Haematology (Mean & ± S.D.) of CF rats

GROUP		Red Blood Cells					White Blood Cells					Platelets (10 ³ /mm ³)	
		Hb (g%)	T-RBC (x10 ⁶ /mm ³)	Hct (%)	MCV (micron ³)	MCHC (g%)	TLC (x10 ³ /m m ³)	Differential Leucocyte Count (%)					
								P	L	E	M		B
Gp. I	Mean	13.4	6.4	37.1	58.2	36.0	14.6	13.0	81.2	2.8	2.8	0.2	320.0
	SD	0.7	0.5	2.0	2.6	0.8	3.9	1.6	2.2	0.8	0.8	0.4	48.8
Gp. II	Mean	14.0	6.8	38.7	56.6	36.4	15.0	14.0	79.8	3.2	3.0	0.0	327.8
	SD	1.2	0.8	5.3	2.3	3.1	2.8	1.6	1.9	0.8	1.0	0.0	47.2
Gp. III	Mean	13.1	6.4	37.1	58.4	35.5	17.5	14.2	80.8	2.6	2.6	0.2	302.6
	SD	0.8	0.7	2.8	2.5	1.1	7.6	1.9	2.3	1.5	0.9	0.4	29.4

Blood Biochemistry

All the blood biochemical values were found to be well within the limits of normalcy and comparable among the treated and control animals of both the sexes. Ranges of variations seen in animals of different groups in values of their metabolic, hepatic and renal function parameters in the male and female animals were within the limits of normalcy.

Table no. 4: Terminal Serum Biochemistry (Mean & ± S.D.) of CF rats

Group		General Metabolic Functions					Liver Functions				Kidney Functions				
		GLU	CHOL	TG	T.P.	ALB	Glob	ALT	AST	ALP	T-BIL	BUN	CRTN	Ca	P
		mg/dl	mg/dl	mg/dl	g/dl	g/dl	g/dl	U/l	U/l	U/l	mg/dl	mg/dl	mg/dl	mg/dl	mg/dl
Gp. I	Mean	87.00	39.40	79.20	5.88	3.60	2.28	47.80	102.80	541.00	0.28	14.60	0.42	10.30	8.38
	± SD	10.12	5.55	32.98	0.68	0.34	0.35	7.76	11.84	75.57	0.04	1.34	0.04	0.94	0.65
Gp. II	Mean	82.40	41.20	71.80	5.74	3.25	2.49	50.00	111.80	532.60	0.24	14.20	0.46	9.94	8.44
	± SD	8.23	4.15	29.23	0.53	0.18	0.52	15.68	33.16	222.18	0.05	2.28	0.05	0.51	1.28
Gp. III	Mean	86.60	40.20	64.00	6.20	3.35	2.85	50.20	116.00	591.80	0.28	15.60	0.46	10.66	8.88
	± SD	12.24	6.10	12.81	0.83	0.72	0.20	5.07	18.75	57.77	0.08	3.21	0.05	1.02	1.31

Autopsy Examination

There was no gross abnormality related to the nature or dose of vaikranta bhasma in any organ/tissue of the treated animals as compared to their controls.

Organ Weights

Absolute weight of left Adrenal of low dose group (Gp. II) was significantly increased, but overall the changes were not significant. Absolute weight of liver and lungs also increased significantly. But, histopathology of both organs appeared normal, so it was an incidental finding.

ROW of liver of grup II was significantly decreased when compared to control group and high dose group. ROW of right kidney of high dose group significantly increased when compared to low dose group. Overall changes were also significant, but histopathology of organs were appeared normal. So, it may be an incidental finding.

Thus, mean value of weights of all the organs (like adrenals, brain, heart, kidneys, gonads, liver, lungs and spleen) showed no significant variations and remained within limits of normalcy in comparison to the control animals.

Table no. 5: Absolute Organ Weights (g, Mean \pm S.D.) of CF rats

Group	Body Wt.	Adrenal		Brain	Gonads		Heart	Kidney		Liver	Lungs	Spleen	
		(g)	Rt		Lt	Rt		Lt	Rt				Lt
Gp	Mean	214.30	0.026	0.024	1.764	1.151	1.161	0.732	0.725	0.711	8.470	1.416	1.157
I	\pm S.D	15.16	0.006	0.004	0.208	0.346	0.349	0.110	0.098	0.080	0.659	0.141	0.301
Gp.	Mean	212.36	0.027	0.029	1.704	1.087	0.998	0.654	0.639	0.665	6.930	1.211	0.867
II	\pm S.D	16.58	0.003	0.007	0.159	0.156	0.272	0.052	0.078	0.082	0.595	0.135	0.202
Gp	Mean	211.46	0.024	0.024	1.811	1.221	1.205	0.763	0.755	0.740	8.755	1.592	1.082
III	\pm S.D	18.25	0.005	0.003	0.051	0.358	0.351	0.122	0.095	0.076	1.607	0.298	0.343

Table no. 6: Relative Organ Weight (g/100 g /body weight, Mean \pm S.D.) of CF rats

Group	Body Wt.	Adrenal		Brai n	Gonads		Hear t	Kidney		Live r	Lung s	Splee n	
		Rt	Lt		Rt	Lt		Rt	Lt				
Gp . I	Mea n	214.30	0.012	0.011	0.829	0.533	0.538	0.340	0.337	0.331	3.955	0.661	0.540
	\pm S.D	15.163	0.003	0.002	0.134	0.145	0.149	0.028	0.022	0.018	0.228	0.037	0.144
Gp . II	Mea n	212.36	0.013	0.014	0.806	0.511	0.465	0.310	0.302	0.315	3.289	0.575	0.410
	\pm S.D	16.581	0.001	0.003	0.091	0.053	0.099	0.044	0.042	0.049	0.480	0.090	0.102
Gp . III	Mea n	211.46	0.011	0.012	0.863	0.584	0.577	0.359	0.357	0.350	4.115	0.752	0.512
	\pm S.D	18.253	0.003	0.002	0.091	0.183	0.185	0.033	0.027	0.015	0.488	0.117	0.149

Histopathological Examination

Microscopic examination revealed isolated instances of infective pathology in both control and treated groups of animals. Instances of such pathology were seen scattered randomly in the respiratory, urinary or gastrointestinal organs of the animals. Findings of microscopic examination of the organs and tissues of animals are described in table no. 7.

Table No. 7: Showing observation of histopathological study

GROUP	ORGAN/TISSUE	OBSERVATION
Gp I	Liver	Focal mononuclear cell collection in 1
	Testis	Quiescent tubules in 3
	Lungs	Increased BALT in 2
Gp II	Lungs	Thickened septa 10
Gp III	Testis	Quiescent tubules in M11

Fig. 1 Photo micrograph of Kidney

Fig. 2 Photo micrograph of liver

Fig. 3 Photo micrograph of BALT lung

Fig. 4 Photomicrograph of lung

Fig. 5 Photomicrograph of Trachea

Fig. 6 Photomicrograph of Testis

CONCLUSION

The test drug is well tolerated since no changes of serious nature could be observed in any of the parameters. This clearly indicates that vaikranta bhasma has no serious toxicological implications on rats upto the oral dose level of 21 mg/ kg. body weight on single administration.

REFERENCES

1. Rathore A.S., Standardization of Vaikranta Bhasma, in relation to its identification, experimental studies and clinical observations, Ph.D. Thesis, IPGT & RA, Gujarat Ayurved University, Jamnagar, 1994..
2. Vagbhatta Rasa, Rasa Ratna Samuchchaya, Commentary by Prof. Dattatreya Anant Kulkarni, Meherchand Lachhamandas Publications, New Delhi, Vol. I, 1998, Ch. 2/68.